

TASK SHIFTING: A NEED FOR CURRENT HEALTH CARE SYSTEM

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INTRODUCTION

World is facing a crisis in human health resources due to a critical shortage of health workers. The shortage is compounded by a high burden of infectious diseases; emigration of trained professionals; difficult working conditions and low motivation. For example, the burden of HIV/AIDS has led to the concept of task shifting being increasingly promoted as a way of rapidly expanding human resource capacity. This refers to the delegation of medical and health service responsibilities from higher to lower cadres of health staff, in some cases non-professionals¹.

Gaps still exist with respect to health programmes, which are unevenly delivered, with rural areas being particularly under-serviced; insufficient support for health care in health care services; and irregular and inconsistent identification and treatment of more common communicable diseases such as depression and anxiety disorders.

The World Health Organization advocates task-shifting, the process of delegating clinical care functions from more specialized to less specialized health workers, as a strategy to achieve the United Nations Millennium Development Goals².

NEED FOR STUDY

This type of study is necessary to align investment in human resources for health with the current and future needs of the population and of health systems, taking account of labour market dynamics and education policies; to address shortages and improve distribution of health

workers, so as to enable maximum improvements in health outcomes, social welfare, employment creation and economic growth.

OBJECTIVE

To assess the gaps of healthcare system and to find out the importance of task shifting.

METHODOLOGY

Study Site: Community

Study Size: 228 Responses

Study Design: Survey

Subjects: Human population

Inclusion Criteria: All adult population

Exclusion Criteria :NA

Data Source :Through various online sources such as Google Scholar, Pubmed, Sciencedirect, Medlineplus, Research Gate.

Material used : Questionnaires

Data analysis :Microsoft EXCEL 2010

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The data collected from 228 subjects reveals that only 7.01% of the subjects have received counseling always; 57.01% have received the counseling sometimes while 14.91% have been counseled mostly, and 19.3% has never been counseled.

Results of the survey reveals, that out of the population, only 14.4% have been counseled more than 10 minutes while 37.3% have been counseled within 1-5 minutes and 21.05% have been counseled less than a minute.

Out of them, 59.65% think that counseling should be given and only 41.66% are satisfied with current health care system while 56.57% are not satisfied. According to 42.1% of the general population, the current health care system is lacking in patient counseling and 19.29% patient care.

CONCLUSION

Our study shows that there is huge burden on health care professionals due to high number of patient load which leads to the improper patient care and finally lead to the degradation in the quality of health care services. Now time has approached when the term task shifting should be taken seriously especially in the health care sectors.

For Future Prospective

Task shifting is a promising policy option to increase the productive efficiency of the delivery of health care services, increasing the number of services provided at a given quality and cost. Future studies should examine the development of new professional cadres that evolve with technology and country-specific labour markets. To strengthen the evidence, skill mix changes need to be evaluated with a rigorous research design to estimate the effect on patient health outcomes, quality of care, and costs.

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